

KEY ISSUES AND CONDITIONS OF IMPLEMENTING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Safarova Sanobar Omontashevna

Alfraganus University Department Pedagogy and Psychology
Associate professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10734023>

Abstract. *This article discusses current issues of introducing inclusive education, the main goal of which is aimed at the widespread implementation of this education system. The main task of our time is to care for children and adolescents in need of special assistance, social support for their rights, and organize the educational process in accordance with the needs and capabilities of children. The article provides basic information and research results on the development of inclusive education. In addition, the problem of what needs to be emphasized for the development of inclusive education is comprehensively covered. Conclusions and proposals for the development of inclusive competencies are also presented.*

Keywords: *special educational needs, inclusive education, integrated education, special pedagogue, development, teaching, children with disabilities, cooperation.*

In our country, the system of social protection of children and provision of educational services to persons with limited physical abilities is perfectly developed.

Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-5712 dated April 29, 2019 of the "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" and PD-4860 dated on October 13, 2020 "Children with special educational needs "On measures to further improve the education system", is one of the promising efforts for every child to find his place in society.

The decision "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs" adopted by the head of our state is important for the further improvement of the inclusive education system and solutions to practical problems. becomes important. In the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoev at the 46th session of the UN Human Rights Council, special attention was paid to strategic issues, including the ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

Considering that there are nearly 1 billion people with disabilities worldwide, this is an extremely important initiative.

In Uzbekistan, measures aimed at wide introduction of inclusive education system, state and non-state cooperation projects on studying international and national work experiences are being implemented. Inclusive education means that children with disabilities receive special education based on special programs along with the main curriculum in the general education schools of the regions where they live, and participate with their peers in classroom activities.

In order to facilitate the educational process, it is necessary to introduce a special pedagogical, psychological and pedagogical support system for the child. A special pedagogue works as a leading expert who conducts and coordinates corrective and educational work with the child.

In inclusive education, the professional skill of the class teacher is the main factor. The requirements for his personal competence are as follows: the teacher's relationship with children

should be humane, and the level of social competence of children with developmental disabilities should be increased.

The main purpose of the conditions for the introduction of inclusive education is in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 Development of inclusive education in Uzbekistan, improvement of the education system for children with special educational needs and improvement of the quality of educational services provided to them, as well as the "Special education" of October 13, 2020 "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special needs" as an implementation of the decision PQ-4860, under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Public Education and Higher and Secondary Special Education It is aimed at promoting inclusive education among teaching staff, psychologists, scientists, students and the public.

In 2020-2025, the implementation of the following issues regarding the introduction and development of inclusive education in the public education system is aimed at:

- improvement of the normative legal framework in the field of inclusive education system;
- training, retraining and professional development of qualified pedagogues for the inclusive education system;
- strengthening the material and technical base of institutions where inclusive education is introduced, necessary literature, methodical manuals; providing equipment and supplies for training in various professions;
- introduction of modern information and communication technologies and innovative projects in the field of inclusive education;
- creating a positive social environment among the population by explaining the right to education of children with special educational needs, the essence of inclusive education;
- implementation of measures aimed at preventing discrimination of children with special educational needs, negative treatment of them;
- implementation of measures aimed at ensuring the right to inclusive education of every child with special educational needs;
- improvement of teaching methods in inclusive education and gradual introduction of individualization principles into the educational process;
- optimization of the number of specialized state educational institutions for children with special educational needs based on the physical and mental needs of students and the territorial location of educational institutions.

All children, regardless of their abilities and circumstances, should be provided with quality education. (UNICEF)

Inclusive education is a philosophy and approach that promotes the participation and achievement of all students, regardless of their different abilities, backgrounds, and characteristics. She strives to create an inclusive learning environment where every student feels valued, respected and supported. However, the successful implementation of inclusive education requires different needs of teachers and students including the knowledge, skills, attitudes and practices required to meet requires inclusive competence.

A child with a disability who needs someone's help in his name. But we forget that not all children are the same.

Among them, there are also children who have the right to receive education and acquire knowledge, as well as healthy children who have little need for help. Although the quality of correctional-pedagogical work of special education and upbringing is at a high level, some problems arise in adapting to our social life because children with special needs do not receive education and upbringing in a healthy environment.

Therefore, it is recognized by the world community that the education of children and adolescents with disabilities in the age-strategic education system causes many negative consequences, and the policy of inclusive education is supported. According to L. S. Vygotsky: "Our special schools are characterized by advantages as well as some disadvantages, which limit their educators to a narrow school community: the deaf, blind or mentally retarded child is the main focus focusing on the existing deficiency in the body, it closes by adapting all conditions to this defect. All this prevents the child from entering real life. Instead of taking the child out of the limited world, the special school usually develops such skills that, as a result, his separatism increases, and the child dives deeper into his own world".

Also, as a result of the democratization of education reform at the international level and the fight against discrimination, the worldview of society has changed, and a new approach, mutual respect, and positive attitude have been formed among people of different categories. The policy of revising the development of the field of special education has begun to be implemented.

Many countries have abandoned "Segregation" education and found it necessary to implement integrated education for children with disabilities. In our country, the main focus is on educating children with disabilities in differentiated special educational institutions, and this educational system is developed.

During the next 10-15 years in Uzbekistan, the issue of inclusion of children with disabilities in the general education system in an integrated and inclusive way is being implemented. The strategy of integration and inclusive education includes the integration of children who are not involved in science into the full special or inclusive education system in general education institutions, and the correctional education institution, due to the distance from the children's residence, to the educational institutions in the areas where they live. consists of teaching.

Integrated education. Currently, in Russia, integrative models of education of children with educational needs based on the principle of normalization are rapidly developing. The advantage of this model is the opportunity for the educational organization and parents to choose the form of integration that is convenient for the child. Various integrated models of teaching children with developmental disabilities have been developed in educational practice.

Permanent partial integration is effective for children who, along with their normally developing peers, can acquire only a small part of the necessary skills and abilities, and can spend only a part of their study and extracurricular time with them.

Temporary partial integration, in which all students of a special group (class), regardless of the level of psychophysiological and speech development, are combined with healthy children at least 2 times a month to conduct various educational activities.

Permanently full-time for children whose mental development is slightly below the age norm, who need systematic and substantial remedial support, but who are able to study together and equally with their normally developing peers in a number of subjects non-integrated.

Episodic integration is the purposeful organization of minimal social interaction of disabled children with their peers.

Continuous full integration can be effective for children who correspond to age norms in terms of psychophysiological and speech development and are psychologically ready to learn together with healthy peers. This model of integrated education is close to adding its own characteristics.

Research shows that inclusive competency development programs contribute significantly to improving teachers' knowledge and skills in meeting the diverse needs of students. These programs include specialized training, co-op teaching opportunities, and ongoing support from experts in the field. Teachers who participate in such programs demonstrate improved teaching practices, increased confidence, and student engagement and achievement.

In order to achieve the above efficiency, the following tasks are carried out in inclusive education:

- creation of necessary material-technical, psychological-pedagogical and correctional conditions for the education of students with disabilities in all educational institutions;
- guaranteeing the right to equality in education among students;
- ensuring the right of disabled children and adolescents to live without separation from their families;
- formation of a friendly and loving attitude towards children and teenagers with disabilities in the society;
- elimination of obstacles between disabled and healthy children with the active participation of society and family, early adaptation to social life;
- increasing the number of active participants in the development of society, further reducing the number of unemployed;
- on the basis of improving the quality of education for all, to grow the state economy and raise the morale of the people.

Inclusive education of children with disabilities is mainly organized in institutions close to the place of residence of children with special needs. Such institutions determine the differences in the various physical needs, individual characteristics, abilities, teaching methods and educational stages of all children and create a differentiated educational system, taking into account their capabilities and levels of mastery.

The most common problems in this regard are the lack of parents' knowledge about inclusive education, the teacher's lack of time to accustom healthy children to it, and the lack of time for the teacher to pay special attention to the disabled child. can be said and so on. Whether we like it or not, we are ingrained with the feeling of pity for the Uzbek people.

Because we feel sorry for him or want to help, we can give an easy task to a child who is studying in front of us with some kind of deficiency, or if he makes a mistake, we can ignore him and evaluate him without paying attention. I believe that it is precisely these situations that sometimes the fact that healthy peers do not like him can be the reason for humiliating him, making fun of him and knocking him to the ground.

In this education, it is necessary not only to pay attention to children with disabilities, but also to consider the mentality of healthy children. A child in need of special help may try to show his peers the qualities that he does not have in order to hide his disability, or he may withdraw from them and try to be as inconspicuous as possible.

In conclusion, we should note that the introduction of inclusive education in our country has its own characteristics. Taking into account the social and economic development of our republic, our national values, and without abandoning or shortening the historically formed special education system, on the contrary, the national module of gradually transitioning to inclusive integration education in cooperation with general education. it is desirable to create.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2020-2025-yillarda Xalq ta'limi tizimida inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirish Konsepsiyasi.(<https://lex.uz/docs/-5044711>).
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 13-oktyabrdagi "Alohida ta'lim ehtiyojlar bo'lgan bolalarga ta'lim-tarbiya berish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-4860-son qarori.
3. Alekhina, S.V. Inklyuziv ta'lim [Matn] / S.V. Alekhina, N.Ya. Semago, A.K. Fadina. - 1-son. - M.: Maktab kitobi, 2010. - 195 b.
4. Artyushenko N.P. Nogiron bolalarni inklyuziv ta'lim orqali o'qitishning tashkiliy-pedagogik shartlari: Dissertatsiya avtoreferati. . dis. . samimiy. ped. Fanlar / Artyushenko N.P.-Tomsk, 2010.-22 p.
5. Batova A.B. Nogiron bolalarni ijtimoiy muhitga integratsiyalashuvining ijtimoiy-pedagogik shartlari: dis. .kand. ped. Fanlar / Batova A.V. M., 2001.-211 b.
6. Mansurov U. J. O'zbekistonda ta'lim sohasidagi islohotlar: inklyuziv ta'lim va yangicha pedagogik yondashuvlar.